

HERPHÆSTUS

Heritage in Europe: new technologies in craft for preserving and innovating futures

Project No. 101095123

Deliverable 3.1

Report on the speculative design process with craft makers

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Abstract	Report of the speculative design trajectory, tracing how art-based research, critical fabulation, and participatory methods were used to engage craft-makers in imagining future craft–technology hybrids. It details three major research output phases, <i>Atmospheres of Craft</i> , <i>A Brave New World</i> , and <i>Brave New World Sketches</i> , showing how each phase generated sensory archives, speculative narratives, public dialogues, and eventually co-created prototypes. It demonstrates how these iterative exhibitions served as tools for reflection, education, and community-building across four craft ecosystems. It further synthesizes craft-makers’ expressed needs and desires around sustainability, community, and the redefinition of progress and time. These findings form the conceptual basis for subsequent project activities, including the Green Living Lab, educational programs, and the upcoming Task 3.2 documentary film.
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About HEPHAESTUS

Working across the **regional craft ecosystems** of **Bassano del Grappa (IT)**, **Bornholm (DK)**, **Dals Långed (SE)**, and **Venice (IT)**, the overarching ambition of HEPHAESTUS is *to bring together cutting-edge technologies with traditional craft to co-create solutions in the form of a suite of tools, methodologies, and business models to make the future of European craft ecosystems socially, culturally, environmentally, and economically sustainable.* HEPHAESTUS will **test and evaluate solutions** co-created across the four regional craft ecosystems within a “**Future of Craft**” **Green Living Lab** situated in Bornholm, a Danish Island and regional municipality given the title of World Craft Region. Ultimately, the project sets out to create a **sustainable network** (especially including regional realities) of heritage sites, cultural and creative sectors, institutions, universities, local, regional and national authorities, enterprises, and other relevant stakeholders engaged in preservation of craft heritage that will take the project’s results, further adapt and deploy them in a broader range of craft ecosystems, and ensure a long- lasting legacy of the HEPHAESTUS project. The work of HEPHAESTUS is organized around six work packages, each responsible for one specific objective related to the overarching ambition, namely:

- Objective 1: Develop new **sustainable business models** for the craft sectors.
- Objective 2: Combine **cutting-edge technologies** with craft materials and processes to research and develop new applications and solutions for the digitisation and innovation of the craft sector to improve sustainability and social innovation.
- Objective 3: Explore visions for the role of **craft in the future**, integrating emerging technologies and contributing to the circular economy, by engaging craft communities in a participatory ideation process.
- Objective 4: Develop a **lifelong learning methodology** and a set of innovative curricula to equip craft-makers with diverse skillsets for innovation.
- Objective 5: Establish a **Green Living Lab** for testing the HEPHAESTUS innovations.
- Objective 6: To design and operationalise a **bespoke dissemination, communication, and exploitation** strategy.

To achieve these objectives, the consortium includes prominent universities, business schools and a private organization selected for their proven knowledge and expertise on craft heritage, craft materials, and the use of digital technologies and cutting-edge technologies in craft, the proposed innovative and original contributions as well as their trustworthiness. A unique value-added brought to the consortium is represented also by the group of third parties, including craft makers and craft associations, as well as Museums and Municipality representatives, from each of the four regional ecosystems.

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1. Executive Summary

This deliverable documents the speculative design process developed within Task 3.1 of the HEPHAESTUS project, directly contributing to Objective 3: To explore visions for the role of craft in the future, integrating emerging technologies and contributing to the circular economy, by engaging craft communities in a participatory ideation process. Specifically, it addresses Sub-Objective O3.1: To design and deliver a collection of speculative prototypes for future craft-technology hybrids.

The report presents the methodology, process, and creative outcomes generated together with craft-makers across four European regional ecosystems (Bornholm, Bassano del Grappa, Venice, and Dals Långed), culminating in a collection of speculative prototypes, visual materials, and conceptual reflections exhibited across multiple public institutions. Through a sequence of artistic and participatory interventions; Atmospheres of Craft (2023), A Brave New World (2024), and Brave New World Sketches (2025), the project re-examines the stereotypical representation of the artisan and foregrounds the complexity of craft practice as entrepreneurial, innovative, and socially and environmentally engaged.

These iterative explorations produced sensory archives, speculative narratives, public exhibitions, interactive workshops, and co-created prototypes that collectively surface the values, needs, and desires of contemporary craft-makers. The results reveal a shared aspiration for a future of craft based on sustainability, circularity, community, and a redefinition of progress rooted in slowness, care, and meaning. The insights generated through collaborative processes provide a foundation for the next stages of WP3 and will inform the documentary film developed under Task 3.2. The work contributes to the wider HEPHAESTUS objective of prototyping desirable futures for craft ecosystems through creative, participatory, and interdisciplinary methodologies, strengthening the bridge between traditional craft practices and emerging technologies.

Disclaimer

This document reflects only the author's view, and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains. This deliverable was originally written in Italian and was then translated and prepared with the support of AI-assisted tools. It was then subsequently revised and edited by the authors to ensure accuracy and conceptual integrity.

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2. About D20 ART LAB

D20 ART LAB is an artistic collective and research laboratory based in Padua (IT) that explores the intersections of technology, art, and design. Within HEPHAESTUS, we are employed at Copenhagen Business School as Art-Based Researchers. We develop new languages to narrate organizations, ecosystems, and communities, investigating the complex interactions between humans and machines, transforming artistic practice into a critical tool for observing, questioning, and reimagining the world we inhabit. Our research delves into the relationships between society, technology, and creativity, aiming to foster unexpected dialogues between body, mind, and machine, and to open new sensory and conceptual horizons. Within this framework, Art-based research (ABR), as theoretically explained later, serves as our main methodological approach: a practice capable of embracing the sensory, affective, and material dimensions of lived experience, expanding the understanding of social phenomena beyond traditional disciplinary boundaries. ABR invites us to immerse ourselves in the processes and contexts we study, alternating between artistic and conventional methods while emphasizing listening, empathy, and engagement with the regeneration of the bonds between culture, community, technology, and nature. We believe that only through mindful and participatory approaches is it possible to imagine shared futures where innovation does not exclude, but rather values, the diversity of knowledge, experiences, and sensitivities. From this perspective, ; becomes a fertile ground for experimenting with plural and transformative forms of knowledge, capable of intertwining art, science, and society, and of proposing visions that foreground sensitivity and sustainability in our ways of inhabiting the world.

3. Purpose and structure of the report

The purpose of this report is to document and reflect upon the speculative design process developed within **Task 3.1** of the HEPHAESTUS project. It presents the methodological framework and creative outputs co-developed with craft-makers, combining ABR (Sharafizad et al., 2023; Christensen-Scheel et al., 2022; Wang et al., 2017), Critical Fabulation (Hartman, 2008; Rosner, 2019; 2018), and Speculative Design Methodologies (Meskus & Tikka, 2022; Auger, 2013). ABR is a qualitative research methodology which uses artistic practices as a form of inquiry whereas creative processes, for instance, visual art, performance, dance, poetic writing, is to generate knowledge that is experiential, embodied, and situated within real social contexts (Fried, 2025). Critical Fabulation, coined by Hartman (2008), is a combination of historical research with imaginative, critical and fictional storytelling to challenge dominant narratives and to surface silenced, overlooked and marginalized perspectives. Lastly, Speculative Design employs hypothetical scenarios (*what if...?*) and designed artefacts to enhance provocation and discussions which can critically explore possible futures rather than predicting them. With these three approaches, this document reports on how artistic and participatory methods have been used within HEPHAESTUS to generate alternative imaginaries for the future of craft, reframe the role of artisans in contemporary society, and highlight the ethical, social, and environmental values that underpin the sustainable craft ecosystems in Europe.

Furthermore, methodologies and processes developed within the Task are intertwined with the tasks in the project. **Task 3.1** further builds on and, at the same time, informs the insights, inspirations and knowledge that have been and is being co-generated within the Hephaestus project. In particular, Task 3.1 builds on, dialogues with and further expand the knowledge co-generated within and across: **Task 1.1** – Mapping the social cultural and political history of the craft ecosystems, contemporary values and controversies, by immersion in each ecosystems and investigating contemporary values and practices in and around craft; **Task 1.2** – Design Thinking Co-creation workshops on technological sustainability and circular economy, whereas workshops, being epistemic encounters defined by their own discursive and co-creative nature, stood as moments of exploration of the role on technology and, at the same time, embodied moments of development and test of critical fabulation, speculation, and ABR as methods; **Task 1.3** – Co-creation of new business models plans for sustainable craft, by highlighting the emergence of structural characteristics that are central to the practice and organization of craft on an economic, social, and environmental level. Similarly, through the imagination and exploration of unusual, fantastical and surprising possibilities for the futures of craft, Task 3.1 feed into **Task 2.1** – Collecting and sharing innovative processes and methodologies for the implementation of new technologies among craft processes, by co-designing possible pathways for technological integrations in craft practices in the future. Finally, D20 ART LAB's work intersected, throughout the life of the Hephaestus project, the activities organised conducted by other actors in the consortium, particularly in the framework of the activities of UGOT, BOFA and UNIVE (**Work Packages 1, 5, 6**). The travels across ecosystems of different iterations of the exhibitions and art works, from parts of *Atmospheres of Craft*, to *A Brave New World*,

and sketches and prototypes designed by the craft makers, contributed to inform and inspire conversations on the future of craft across work packages, craft makers and public.

The report records the evolution of the collaborative research phases. From sensory exploration and narrative reconstruction to speculative co-design, while providing insights into how imagination can be mobilized as a critical and relational instrument for knowledge production. In doing so, it aims to contribute to the wider objectives of **Work Package 3**, which is to envision and prototype desirable futures for the craft sector through inclusive and creative practices. It also aims to prepare the work for the documentary which is part of **Task 3.2**.

The report is structured as follows:

Section 1 introduces the conceptual and methodological foundations of the project, focusing on the role of ABR and the creation of the exhibition *Atmospheres of Craft* as a dialogical and sensory exploration of European craft ecosystems. **Section 2** describes how speculative and narrative methods were employed in *A Brave New World* to rethink progress, technology, and sustainability through counterfactual storytelling and collaborative reflection. **Section 3** presents the results of co-creation with artisans, including their speculative prototypes, narratives, and reflections on the future of craft, articulating a collective vision rooted in sustainability, community, and ethical making.

Additionally, it is essential that we acknowledge our positionality as researchers and artists. Drawing on Donna Haraway's concept of *situated knowledges* (2013), we recognize that our perspectives are partially constructed and shaped by the cultural, institutional, and disciplinary contexts in which we operate. Moreover, our position in the project is shaped by the fact that we are researchers and artists, which leads us to engage with craft makers through the sharing of practices and common ground. This approach generates a form of professional intimacy, where trust emerges from a shared language and way of working, making emotional involvement an integral part of the method rather than a marginal aspect. This engagement is not a side effect, but a constitutive element that allows us to perceive nuances that would otherwise remain invisible, such as uncertainties, economic pressures, care and attention to tools and the quality of work. Our interpretations emerge through continuous dialogue with the craft-makers and other participants, rather than from a position of neutrality or detachment. This hybrid stance, suspended between artistic practice and research, does not diminish rigor but redefines it, opening a space of knowledge that arises from shared experience rather than analytical distance. Being Italian ourselves adds another level of awareness when working with the Italian craft ambassadors. Yet, engaging with contexts in Denmark and Sweden pushed us to consider alternative possibilities and perspectives, raising questions and reflections. This cultural gap proved to be a methodological resource, enabling us to observe practices without taking anything for granted, just as the exchange with the scholars is always a source of further reflection on our thinking and practice. This reflexive stance aligns with the principles of ABR (Leavy, 2020), which prioritizes immersion, empathy, and creative co-production, and with Paulo Freire's (1996) vision of inquiry as a dialogical and transformative process. Rather than aiming to produce universal truths, this report seeks to open plural, situated, and collaborative spaces for reflection, imagination, and co-creation.

Lastly, throughout the document, ‘we’ refers to us, Raffaella Rivi and Sergio Marchesini, together building D20 ART LAB. Almost all the images in this report, except for a few taken with a cellphone, are an integral part of our research.

4. Introduction

4.1 Deconstructing the Artisan Stereotype: Complexity, Identity, and Place

Our work within the HEPHAESTUS project, specifically through the engagement of the reading seminars organized by WP1, led us to question the stereotypes tied to the figure of the artisan and how it might be represented from a perspective capable of reflecting the complexity of the subject. This reflection has grown over time, shaped also by our professional experience in Italy, a country historically marked by a strong manufacturing tradition (Becattini 2002; Bellandi et al., 2022).

The stylistic tropes of the artisan’s representation tend to repeat with a certain insistence, often offering a superficial vision of the phenomenon. Yet they strongly influence the collective imagination, crystallizing these figures into a kind of icon disconnected from reality (Sennett, 2008). As we learned from the reading groups organized by UGOT, engaging all WPs, in the common imagination, the artisan appears as a mythologized figure, suspended, outside of time, shut away in a small workshop, lit by a grazing light, surrounded by modest working tools. A character, usually male and elderly, embodying a kind of simplicity mingled with wisdom in his way of life, wrapped in a romantic aura linked to ancient knowledge, and resistant to the new (Risatti 2009). Figure 1 exemplifies the craft maker, created by AI. Our approach to using AI as an artistic tool will be deepened later in the report (see Section 4.4).

Figure 1: Image from Leonardo.ai, prompt “typical craft maker in Europe”

Yet, in the collective imagination, it is a trade considered “minor,” whose products do not belong to the logic of mass production or large-scale economies, and which for this reason remains on the margins of contemporaneity (Löfgren & Ehn, 2010). It is a profession observed by society with an ambivalent gaze, oscillating between admiration, compassion, and doubt, bringing it dangerously close to the figure of the artist (Dormer 1997; Adamson 2013). As often happens with artists, artisans too can be subject to excessive idealization, which creates a form of social vulnerability, since their work is not always recognized as a genuine professional practice. Craftwork is sometimes perceived as a vocation or passion rather than as a productive activity that requires rigor, investment, care, and preparation, in addition to its artistic and creative dimension, thus making their economic legitimization more complex.

These stereotypes reduce the artisan to a folkloric image, made of hands, workshops, and tradition. The narrative often unfolds through detail: the close-up, the meticulous gesture, the isolated sound of a strictly analog tool reverberating in silence. An evocative portrayal, yet one that leaves essential aspects of the artisan’s work in the shadows (Ingold, 2012).

With *Atmospheres of Craft*, our first artwork within the HEPHAESTUS project, we began our investigation of the practices and their localities from a distance: in each ecosystem we explored the nature that surrounds it, the people who inhabit it and the relationships that are created there, the history that has defined it, the traditions, the voice of its poets, and its ability to reinvent and transform itself. We began our investigation with a simple but meaningful question: what makes a place so unique that it becomes the ideal ground for craft to grow and take shape? What gives a place its identity? Some of the results of this investigation are shown in Figure 2 and 3.

As the project progressed and we encountered artisans from the four HEPHAESTUS ecosystems, we realized how important it is to focus on certain characteristics that are fundamental to understanding the layered nature of such a complex profession. These include the capacity for experimentation, an entrepreneurial mindset, openness to innovation, and attention to the environment, not only in terms of raw materials but about society as a whole.

Figure 2: The Nardini "Bubbles" designed by M. Fuksas, Bassano del Grappa

Figure 3: Allinge, Bornholm

4.2 Capturing the elusive: starting from art-based research

As Leavy (2020) emphasizes, ABR does not merely produce data, but generates aesthetic experiences capable of stimulating new forms of understanding and emotional resonance. Walking in the rain and stopping at a deserted campsite, meeting a migrant who shares their story, looking at old photographs with an elderly woman encountered on the street, all of these experiences highlight the value of lived experience, activating perception and other levels of learning, as suggested by Donna Haraway (2013) with the concept of *situated knowledge*. According to Haraway, knowledge can never be neutral or universal; it is always partial, embodied, and positioned. Every form of knowing emerges from the encounter between the observer and what is observed, and is shaped by the social, cultural, and material context in which it occurs. Reflections, encounters, and discoveries are co-constructed with participants, constantly reminding us of the ethical dimension of research, which must consider the reciprocity of relationships and the complexity of different ecosystems without claims to universality.

Figure 4: Heidi Hentze and Nynne Rosenkrantz Christiansen, Bornholm Craft Ambassadors

During our several ABR journeys, we collected testimonies and visions using our artistic tools such as photographs, videos, and recordings of sounds and voices (see Figures 4, 5). Recording a traditional song inside an empty factory or photographing an elderly couple sunbathing at the end of summer is not merely a decorative act, but a form of interpretation and knowledge of the world, allowing us to intuit symbolic values that may become the focal point of a story. Artistic forms are not only means to communicate knowledge (Eisner, 2008) but can also serve as tools to produce it, enabling us to grasp aspects of reality that elude purely analytical or quantitative description. Aesthetic and imaginative thinking does not

simply complement research; it constitutes a central mode of exploration, allowing access to the complexity of human phenomena in a profound and pluralistic way. As McNiff (1998) points out, the activation of creative and imaginative thinking opens new pathways to understanding complex cultural and social phenomena.

The many questions and contradictions that emerged from this journey have become the starting point for our research that pushes us to have a strong dialogic and participatory intent.

Figure 5: Dals Långed. New platform co-created with arch. Daniel Winterbottom and the community

4.3 Atmospheres of Craft. Asking as co-construction of meaning

The next step was the reworking of the collected material and the identification of points of connection between the different ecosystems. This process was not limited to the production of new interpretations but also generated a direct impact on the work of both the academic team and the craft makers involved, reinforcing the participatory intent and shaping modes of interaction within a genuine *safe zone*. The first HEPHAESTUS exhibition, called *Atmospheres of Craft*, represented an important moment to share our reading of the ecosystems and to activate a *mirror game*, in which reciprocal gazes made an open and plural dialogue possible. In this space of exchange, the traditional categories of belonging,

such as artists, academics, and craft makers were suspended and reshuffled, allowing new relational configurations to emerge.

Figure 6: Atmospheres of Craft, Palazzo Sturm, May 2023, Bassano del Grappa (IT)

Atmospheres of Craft took place at Palazzo Sturm in Bassano del Grappa (IT) from 27/05 to 30/06/2023 (see Figures 6, 7). The exhibition was structured into four rooms, and it gathered and organized the materials collected during our journey. It began with *Souvenirs*, the first room, featuring everyday objects, materials, images, and artifacts that capture memories of moments lived along the way. Postcards created from our photographs, along with captions, tell small stories, constructing a shared memory of the places and experiences encountered (see Figure 7). The second room, *Videography*, invites reflection on the role of craftsmanship across different contexts, exploring the interplay between nature, landscape, and tradition. The ideas gathered during the journey are expressed through statements and questions, revealing the complexity and ambiguity of the subject while opening new perspectives. In *Voices*, the third room, fragments of conversations, memories, anecdotes, nursery rhymes, and songs from people directly or indirectly connected to the artisanal ecosystems emerge like echoes of our journey, conveying the lively and participatory atmosphere of these communities. Finally, *RadioScapes*, the last room, engages visitors as active participants, allowing them to create their “own atmosphere” through an interactive device that manipulates the collected sounds. In this way, the atmosphere becomes a tangible, immersive experience, a dynamic, ever-changing process that transforms and recombines according to the actions of those who inhabit it.

Figure 7: Atmospheres of craft, Palazzo Sturm, Bassano del Grappa (IT)

The audio/visual material represents the moment of crystallization of the knowledge process: what until then had been experience, relationship, or intuition takes on a concrete form and becomes an object capable of sparking reflection, opening new starting points, and shifting perspectives, redefining roles and positions. In this way, the research contributes to dismantling implicit hierarchies and generating more horizontal connections among the participants. The work thus takes shape as a tangible and exhibited form of “evidence,” which does not close but rather inaugurates a space of dialogue and co-construction of meaning.

A fundamental element of this process—which gradually took shape for us as a method—was the decision to preserve and highlight the questions that emerged during the initial phase of the work. More than simple tools of inquiry, these questions have taken on the role of epistemic devices. They not only trace the path we have followed but also act as catalysts for reflection, generating spaces for discussion and opening up unexpected interpretive possibilities. In this sense, the question is not conceived as a preliminary step toward a definitive answer, but as a dynamic trigger that keeps the field of research open and preserves its dialogical and plural dimension. For Freire, to question does not simply mean to seek answers but, as he states in *The Pedagogy of the Oppressed* (2020) to stimulate a process of critical and shared learning, in which the act of asking becomes itself an exercise of freedom and transformation. In this sense, the questions collected along our path take shape as generative moments that reinforce the participatory intent of the research and contribute to redefining the relationships among the different actors involved. The formulation of the questions, deliberately “irregular” from a grammatical perspective, reflects

the path we have followed (see Figure 8). It does not aim to provide definitive answers, but to give voice to a reflection born from observation aligning with an inquisitive spirit of research, conceived as the art of posing problems rather than solving them. They represent an opening, an invitation to new questions and to a shared dialogue, in which the public, craft makers, and scholars can contribute with their own perspectives. Our standpoint is meant to open: a stimulus for exchange rather than a conclusive statement.

The videos continued to “live” even after the exhibition, becoming agile tools for exchange and sharing during various moments of dissemination and public engagement, thanks to their ability to emotionally involve those who watch them. The questions emerged from observation and from the need, during our travels, to engage with people and the surrounding environment. We made an effort to remain as open as possible to the idea of discovery, cultivating a willingness to embrace the unexpected and to follow events as they unfolded. In this sense, the act of observing and asking questions is intertwined with the practice of traveling itself, becoming a dynamic and generative process in which direct experience and curiosity serve as essential tools for understanding the nuances and complexities of the world around us. Some of the themes that emerged have become guiding principles for our future work, such as the relationship with the environment: the seasons are perceived and experienced very differently between the North and the South, influencing the relationship with the community and the social fabric. Other relevant aspects include time management, the need to find one’s own space in the economy while remaining attentive to resources and sustainability, the relationship between beauty and functionality, managing interdisciplinarity and the delicate balance between quality and quantity.

Figure 8: Frame from video *Atmospheres of Craft*

4.4 A Brave New World. The speculative and critical dialog with scholars

The reflections developed within *Atmospheres of Craft* became the foundation from which a new project took shape: *A Brave New World*, built around the values of sustainability, circularity, and the specialization of labor; which are values that constitute the very backbone of craftsmanship. Values that stand in sharp contrast to the logic of mass production, evoking a world where time, care, and manual skill define the very meaning of making. A kind of utopia, imagining a *divergent story*: a world in which the relationship with resources, modes of production, trade, and consumption are radically different, because they are closer to those typical of artisanal production. What would such a world look like? And how might a production system alternative to capitalism as we know it impact the environment, politics, the educational system, urban planning, and lifestyles?

Moreover, *A Brave New World* also investigated what principles might underpin a craft-centered world, including:

- Craft-led innovation, where technological advancement supports rather than replaces human expertise.
- Sustainable production models, grounded in material stewardship and circular resource use.
- Cooperation alongside competition, creating more balanced and equitable economic and social structures.
- Education and apprenticeship as central cultural institutions.
- Community-based living and alternative urban planning prioritizing shared resources rather than consumption.
- Resilience to crises through local knowledge, distributed production, and shared responsibility.
- Debates on the role of artificial intelligence in supporting, challenging, or transforming craft practices.

The installation has evolved through several iterations, each deepening the dialogue and expanding participation:

- **Brave New World 1.0** (Dals Långed, April/May 2024): first public presentation and scholarly discussion on historical alternatives to mass production. The same exhibition was on display at BOFA Resource Day in Bornholm in August 2024.
- **Brave New World 1.5** (Ca' Foscari, Venice, November 2024): expanded focus on issues such as overtourism, stereotypes in AI imagery, and public engagement through interactive feedback.
- **Brave New World 2.0** (Röhsska Museum, Gothenburg, May 2025): co-creation with craft ambassadors to contribute speculative prototypes, statements, and video reflections.

The methodology that guided our work throughout the process of developing the *Brave New World* iterations is *Critical Fabulation*, an approach introduced by Sadiya Hartman (2008) and reinterpreted by Daniela Rosner (2018) that combines storytelling and design thinking to rethink traditional systems and research practices. The term *fabulations*, derived from the Latin *fabulatus* (“to tell as a fable or myth”), refers to a narrative method that intertwines the real and the imaginary to explore new ways of interpreting the past and imagining the future. Rosner combines this “fabled” practice with design thinking, exploring the past, present, and future through a form of “investigative activism” (Mthoko, Adamu & Lazem, 2023).

Critical Fabulations encourage researchers to question the stories underpinning design and to deconstruct established practices, opening ethical and creative possibilities. Rosner (2018) identifies four main tactics: building alliances across diversity, interfering with dominant narratives, recovering traces of erasure, and extending forms of circulation. Through these practices, Critical Fabulations allow for the reinterpretation of methodologies and narratives, generating alternative and more inclusive perspectives in contemporary design.

To bring this first “release” of *A Brave New World* to life, we engaged in a speculative dialogue with researchers in economic history, management, and organization from the partner Universities of the *HEPHAESTUS* project—among them prof. Giovanni Favero and prof. Marta Gasparin who became an integral part of our creative process. This collaborative work enabled a dynamic and fruitful exchange with the scientific community, capable of generating questions, perspectives, and viewpoints that challenged established assumptions on both sides. The encounter between different languages—the analytical and systematic nature of academic research and the imaginative and experimental drive of artistic practice—opened unexpected spaces for exploration. Within this shared terrain, theoretical concepts were translated into narrative and visual possibilities, while artistic insights stimulated new lines of critical inquiry.

The conceptual foundation of the project emerged from imagining a disruptive and unforeseeable “black swan” event at the end of the 19th century—a moment of rupture capable of radically altering the dominant industrial paradigm. Instead of leading Europe and the world into the era of mass production and standardization, this hypothetical turning point redirects history toward the continued evolution of artisanal production systems. This speculative premise allowed us to question how technological, social, and cultural development might have unfolded if craftsmanship, rather than mechanization, had remained the core driver of progress.

The first version of *Brave New World 1.0* released at the annual *HEPHAESTUS* Symposium in Dals Långed in early May 2024 (see **T1.1**), unfolded through 16 panels, each accompanied by captions forming the timeline of this new utopian world—its title paying homage to the writer Aldous Huxley (1932) (see Figure 9). We imagined the starting point to be 1848, a pivotal moment in the shaping of the European and global order, extending through to the present day. In this reconstruction, the imagined black swan disruption opens the possibility for a radically different 20th century, prompting us to explore how historical trajectories might have shifted without the wars that shaped industrial and political systems as we know them. What would have happened, for example, if Hitler had been admitted to the Academy of Fine Arts? Would history have taken a different course? We tried to imagine

cities, homes, families, and transportation systems organized in new ways, opening up possibilities that are still little explored in our daily lives, and to envision a more balanced relationship with the environment, based on alternative forms of energy and engineering capable of reducing the impact of our habits. In this exercise of imagination, we explored possible scenarios in which living together could be transformed, becoming more sustainable, inclusive, and attentive to the planet's resources. Which daily 'comforts' would we be willing to give up in order to contribute concretely to reshaping the world in a fairer and more sustainable way?

This exhibition materialized a space of speculation during the Symposium (see Figure 10), and its location in an ex-industrial building amplified its speculative impact. Throughout the event, it was activated at different moments and contributed to shaping the craft-oriented atmosphere in which the design-thinking workshop on the role of community and the future of craft was held (**Task 1.1**).

1925 Japanese Delegation visiting Saint Petersburg

Japan's victory over Russia in the Russo-Japanese War (1905) marks the beginning of a phase of economic and cultural expansion of the Japanese empire in Asia first, and from the 1920s in Europe.

The Japanese model is linked to an idea of agile production focused on quality, which is an ideal continuation of the ancient craft tradition.

1955 Advertisement campaign for the National Laundry, Berlin

Don't do this at home! You don't need a washing machine, you need new friends. Visit the national laundry.

The model of non-price competition protected by local governments has the effect of making products more expensive, resulting in an emphasis on durability and quality for everyday products and the spread of sharing systems for more expensive products.

The public sector supports the promotion of a lifestyle compatible with the production model through media campaigns and incentives, focused on the reuse and sharing of spaces and services. These places of access to common services also become places of social interaction and discussion.

1970 Primitive Makers flash mob, Copenhagen

By 1970, craft makers are highly regarded as visionaries and a driving force in society. They influence policy-making and advocate for continuous improvements in the production and distribution sectors.

They raise questions about sustainable resource usage, intellectual property rights, and circular economies. Incubator companies are created to fund craft makers with innovative ideas that can contribute to the common good. Some of them become public figures and deliver keynote speeches at yearly international craft expositions.

Within the public debate on craft a new group stands out, taking inspiration from the Swedish slöjd: the Primitive Maker Alliance uses guerrilla marketing techniques to push for a more democratic publicly-accessible idea of craft-making. They advocate for the utilization of basic hand tools commonly found in households, readily available and affordable materials, and easily accessible machinery. They propose a practice that is more flexible than institutionally hierarchical, structured without being strictly organized.

2017 Donald Trump Campaign

Donald Trump is a famous fashion designer who became a star thanks to his appearances in the media after inventing a type of environmentally friendly dye. Criticized by many for his populist slogans and appreciated by others for his strong support of the artisan sector, he ran for the presidency of the United States in 2017.

The current state of media is dominated by the Internet, a federated and distributed information system that has completely moved to a public 'blockchain' to guarantee democratic access, data protection, freedom of expression and measures have been taken to avoid concentration, monopolies, exploitation, algorithmic manipulation and platform lock-in. The open source movement has become the dominant innovation force.

Figure 9: Various panels from A Brave New World 1.0 exhibition

Figure 10: A Brave New World 1.0, first release at Hephaestus Symposium in Dås Langed, May 2024

For the production of the images, we chose to work with artificial intelligence (AI). On the one hand, this allowed us to experiment within our artistic practice with a technology that is currently transforming our present; on the other hand, it prompted us to reflect on what it means for an artist to engage with such a powerful tool. It is clear that current generative AI models reflect only the culture, knowledge, and perspectives of the part of the world and society that created (or financed) them. As such, they offer fertile ground for exploring contradictions, clichés, hallucinations, and blind spots of technologically dominant Western society, but at the same time, they pose a threat if end users assume these representations to be complete or correct, thereby propagating a biased vision of the world along with its stereotypes. By grounding the work in real historical events, we sought to imagine how different configurations of the world might have reshaped both collective and individual

destinies. This process, rather than being a mere ucronistic experiment (Carrère, 2024), prompted a reflection not only on paths history might have taken but also on the latent possibilities that remain obscured by dominant narratives.

From this perspective, certain concepts proved particularly difficult to reconsider—among them, the idea of progress, understood both as technical or material advancement and as a complex entanglement of social, ethical, and political dimensions (Banerjee & Arjaliès, 2021). Modernity has often been built upon a linear notion of development, separating nature from culture and projecting a sense of inevitability. In contrast, alternative approaches invite us to move away from these singular and deterministic narratives, embracing open and multiple histories capable of holding together hybridity and uncertainty. To question progress, therefore, means to confront the power it exerts as one of the founding myths of modernity. It is not merely a promise of emancipation, but also a device that has justified exclusion, exploitation, and domination (Holm & Beyes, 2022; Vijay et al., 2025). Rethinking it requires opening imaginative spaces where alternatives can emerge—paths that do not follow an inevitable or predetermined trajectory. Working with alternative configurations of history allowed us to challenge this legacy: to imagine futures that are not mere projections of the past, but scenarios integrating the pluralities of the present and enabling new, yet-unimagined forms of coexistence.

This process generated new questions, which, in the first version of the exhibition presented during the HEPHAESTUS Symposium in May 2024 in Dals Långed organized by **WP1** were translated into postcards (see Figures 11, 12, 14) accompanying the exhibition panels, and later sparked further engagement during the presentation of the exhibition at Resource Day at BOFA in August 2024 (see Figure 13); for more details see D5.2) by **WP5**.

Figure 11: A Brave New World 1.0 postcard

A brave new world
Tales from a craft Utopia.

What would the world look like if our present were built on artisanal foundations rather than being the full, and now unsustainable, expression of industrial civilization?

CAN THE THINGS YOU DO
 WITH YOUR HANDS
 GIVE A NEW SHAPE
 TO YOUR TRUE SELF?

Venice Biennale, a great success for the Austrian painter A. Hitler, 1944

Funded by the European Union
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HEPHAESTUS

created by **D20 ART LAB**

Figure 12: A Brave New World 1.0 postcard

Figure 13: Exhibition A Brave New World 1.0 at Resource Day, BOFA, Rønne August 2024

4.4.1 Postcards from A Brave New World. Not only a souvenir but an educational tool

The postcards (see Figure 11, 12, 14) were conceived as educational tools that go far beyond the simple function of souvenirs or mementos: they act as mediators of knowledge and reflection. Their power lies in their ability to transform an exhibition space into a context of active learning, where visitors are not merely observers but are invited to interact, interpret, and formulate their own responses. In this sense, postcards function as tools for experiential learning, following the principles outlined by Dewey and Kolb, in which direct experience and reflection become engines for generating meaning (Dewey, 1986; Kolb, 2014; Seaman, Brown, & Quay, 2017).

Figure 14: A Brave New World 1.0 postcard

Each postcard, with its deliberately provocative question, stimulates critical thinking and discussion, encouraging participants to engage with different perspectives, challenge established assumptions, and generate innovative ideas. By not requiring specialized knowledge, postcards make the learning process accessible and inclusive, allowing individuals with diverse backgrounds—craftspeople, students, academics, or general visitors—to engage in dialogue on complex topics, transforming the object into a device for co-learning (Pope et al., 2024; Young, 2024). Moreover, postcards can be used in a variety of educational and practical contexts: workshops, guided discussions, individual reflection exercises, or collaborative activities. Their modularity and flexibility make them adaptable to multiple scenarios, capable of fostering both personal reflection and collective dialogue, as emphasized in Wenger's theories on learning communities (Wenger, 2012) and in critical pedagogy approaches. In this way, postcards not only facilitate the transmission of

knowledge but also become generative devices, producing new narratives, and creating connections between experiences, perspectives, and disciplines.

Finally, the physical and tangible nature of the postcards contributes to a concrete sensory experience, enhancing the cognitive and emotional impact of the questions. The possibility of hanging the postcards in the space and seeing them all together, alongside the exhibition panels, provides an additional stimulus, offering an overall view that allows visitors to perceive connections and relationships between the different questions.

4.5 Brave New Talks: About Progress

We had the chance to test these tools during the exhibition days in Dals Långed in May 2024, engaging both academics and artisans in a feedback session on the exhibition and a broader reflection on the theme of progress. The entire process was documented and resulted in a short docufilm, *About Progress* (see Figure 15 and [online exhibition](#)), in which we presented an overview of the reflections of the participants involved. From both groups, shared needs clearly emerged:

- rethink the notion of time
- promoting a better reconciliation between private life and work
- ensuring equity and sustainability

Another important reflection suggests that among young people a kind of ‘counter-reaction’ is beginning to emerge — a desire to return to a life rooted, away from social media and the web. Finally, it also emerged that cultural activities and craftsmanship could represent the necessary resources to bring new life to places and spaces that technological progress has depopulated by relocating activities elsewhere.

Figure 15: Frame from *Brave New Talks: about progress*

These moments of shared reflection not only fostered mutual trust but also encouraged dialogue and collaboration and co-construct insights, turning the exhibition into an interactive and participatory environment.

Applied to our process, this perspective led us to feel the urgency of giving space not only to historical or academic traces, but also to the voices of those who embody those values in their everyday lives. It is in this direction that we decided to directly involve the artisans, transforming them into co-authors of the project and recognizing their knowledge not only as an object of research but as a living and indispensable contribution to the construction of new shared narratives (Ingold, 2013).

4.6 A *Brave New-You World*. Reframing Communication and Participation in the Speculative Process

The exhibition of *A Brave New World 2.0* in Venice, (October–December 2024) organized by **UNIVE**, bridging **WP6, 3 and 1**, allowed us to deepen the project and reflect on its modes of communication (see Figure 16). This was also an opportunity for us to further explore the issue of the stereotypes embedded in artificial intelligence, to which we dedicated several panels. The stereotypes already present in society — gender-based, ethnic, professional, geographic, aesthetic — can infiltrate datasets and models, reproducing and amplifying existing biases. This led us to extend the reflection to Venice itself, a city often portrayed

through visual and narrative clichés, and to dedicate a special focus to the theme of overtourism.

From the feedback collected among visitors and craft makers, a critical point emerged: the captions were sometimes too complex for those unfamiliar with the subject. This led us to rethink a possible future installation — one that would be more accessible in its content and capable of including a more “concrete” testimony, giving voice to those who work daily with the values and themes of the project. The next step was therefore to involve the project’s ambassadors in the speculative process, in order to make the imagined futures more tangible and credible — transforming ideas into experiences rooted in reality. This approach also allowed us to explore their needs, aspirations, and desires more deeply.

A first testing ground for experimenting with inclusive methods was the *finissage* workshop held at Ca’ Foscari University (**UNIVE**) (see Figure 17) . In collaboration with researchers, we launched an open call addressed to everyone, with the aim of collecting reflections on two central themes of *A Brave New World 2.0*, reinterpreted from the perspective of the city: overtourism and transformations of work (see Figure 18). The active participation of the public showed how, once stimulated by the exhibition, people did not merely observe but began to question, to ask, and to share personal experiences and diverse points of view.

The core of the debate thus became the possibility of rethinking needs and necessities. What if the city were accessible only to medium- or long-term visitors? What if the concept of vacation included visiting other craft makers and intertwining with the idea of work? What if visiting a city also meant co-creating something within it?

Figure 16: A Brave New World 2.0 exhibition at Ca' Foscari (UNIVE), Venice Oct-Dec 2024

Figure 17: A Brave New You World, Workshop at Ca' Foscari (UNIVE), Venice Oct-Dec 2024

Through this speculative process, we were able to observe how, starting from a single input, a pathway of imagination and dialogue could unfold — nourished by personal ideas, fantasies, and desires. In conclusion, we introduced a critical and conscious use of visualization, translating ideas into visual prompts and seeking an iconographic output that could be both original and capable of conveying the complexity of the thinking that had emerged (see Figure 18).

The act of transforming an idea into a visual prompt involved a double movement: on the one hand, the need to clarify thought, to make it more concrete and articulated; on the other, the openness to a margin of indeterminacy, where the image-generation machine introduces unexpected, disorienting, and at times unsettling elements that enrich the interpretative process.

Figure 18: AI images generated during the A Brave New You World workshop with participants

This passage also allowed us to reflect on the role of image generation technologies within artistic research and speculative design processes: not as tools of automatic representation, but as dialogic partners capable of producing hybrid visions — suspended between reality and possibility. The image thus becomes not merely an outcome but a threshold — a territory where collective thought takes shape, encounters itself, and is continuously reconfigured.

5.0 Brave New World Sketches, a co-creative process

The new edition of the exhibition (2.5) in Gothenburg took place from May 20 to June 4, 2025, in the only Swedish museum dedicated explicitly to Design and Craft: the **Röhsska Museum of Design and Craft**. For this event, organized by **UGOT** (bridging **WP1, WP2 & WP6**), we decided to involve the HEPHAESTUS craft ambassadors more directly in the speculative process. The aim was to produce prototypes that expressed their needs or aspirations in relation to a personal practice, object, idea, or philosophy, reimagined within the utopian world of *A Brave New World* (see Figures 20, 21, 22). In their case, this translated into the development of prototypes: sketches on paper, design concepts, photographs, or multimaterial mood boards — including collages and AI-assisted compositions — used to present their project proposals.

The speculative process evolved from the visual to the operational level, linking imagination to concrete action. From October 2024 to May 2025, we acted as curators through a series of online and in-person meetings, during which we invited the HEPHAESTUS craft ambassadors to actively take part in the project (see Figure 19).

Figure 19: Meeting HEPHAESTUS' ambassadors during the preparation of the prototypes

The meetings were conceived as moments of dialogue in which to collectively reflect on the themes proposed by our utopian world — such as social equity, cultural and social evolution, the relationship with the environment, globalization, and cultural exchange — creating a space for listening and mutual understanding. The creative process was guided by specific constraints and conditions defined by our guidelines, transforming artistic practice into a stimulus that disrupted and reactivated the artisans' everyday routines.

Through play, the use of their own language, and collaborative modes during the brainstorming phase, we were able to observe and engage with their work from new

perspectives. This approach opened up meaningful spaces for dialogue — for instance, on the role of technology within craft practices — sparking reflections on the opportunities and limitations of innovation in creative and traditional contexts, as well as on fundamental concepts inherent to their practice, such as the notion of time.

The collaboration with the craft makers therefore went beyond merely documenting their activities: it created the conditions for a genuine co-production of meaning, in which their practical experience, skills, and ideas became an integral part of the creative process and of the research itself. This process also sparked a strong sense of mutual curiosity, leading us to organize an open call to share their projects with all participants.

Figure 19B: Presentation of “The Library of Minds” by HEPHAESTUS craft ambassador Nynne Rosencrantz Christiansen

The process reached a further stage of growth and exchange during the annual HEPHAESTUS Symposium, held in Bornholm in June 2025, where some ambassadors took part in a roundtable discussion that opened new spaces for dialogue and stimulated additional interests (see Figure 19B). The co-creative prototype development phase not only deepened the speculative dimension of the project but also offered a unique entry point into the lived realities, constraints, and aspirations of contemporary craft-makers. By shifting from conceptual speculation to hands-on experimentation, the process revealed recurring themes, values, and tensions that transcend geographical differences and point to a shared vision for the future of craft. The following section synthesizes these reflections, grouping them into key areas that emerged across discussions, workshops, interviews, and prototype development.

Figure 20: A Brave New World 2.5 exhibition at Röhsska Museum in Gothenborg, May 2025

Figure 21: A Brave New World 2.5 exhibition at Röhsska Museum in Gothenborg, May 2025

Figure 22: A Brave New World 2.5 exhibition at Röhsska Museum in Gothenborg, May 2025

5.1 Needs and desires of craft makers

Craftspeople interviewed for the *Brave New World* project express a deep desire for a future of craft that prioritizes sustainable and human-centered practices, moves beyond mass production and overconsumption, and fosters community, connection, and the intrinsic value of their work (see Figure 23). Their reflections also express crucial needs regarding knowledge, skills, tools, and a redefinition of progress and time (see Table).

In the following sections (3.1, 3.2, 3.3, 3.4, 3.5, 3.6) we present the key themes and perspectives from the artists and craftspeople, with author attributions where they are possible, grouped in five macro areas: sustainability and circularity, moving beyond mass production, product personalization and endurance, community and connection, the role of the maker, skill and continuous learning, meaning of progress. The following table summarizes the key themes and perspectives.

Theme	Key Insights	Representative Quotes	Implications
Sustainability & Circularity	Resource awareness; local material cycles; ethical making	“My work is about sustainability and circularity”. -A. M. S. Jensen	Support tools for regenerative material sourcing and reuse
Beyond Mass Production	Opposition to speed and disposability	“Optimization without soul”. -Te.Ra. Studio	Promote unique, durable, repairable products
Community & Connection	Collective learning and shared spaces	“Create a sense of belonging”. -K. Hallberg	Support maker hubs, shared tools, and social economies
Valuing Craft & the Maker	Visibility of process and embodied knowledge	“A spirit within an object”. - Terra Studio	Advocacy, education, and cultural recognition
Skills & Tools	Learning through hands, intergenerational knowledge	“Connect hand and head”. -R. Curran	Reinforce training infrastructures and manual practice
Redefining Progress & Time	Human-paced systems and balance	“Progress could mean stepping back”. - workshop participant	Rethinking growth metrics and work–life values

Figure 23: HEPHAESTUS' craft ambassadors in Bornholm and in Italy

5.1.1 Sustainability and Circularity

The concept of sustainability is at the heart of the craft makers' view of the world. Across all the eco-systems we have visited, across the different generations, all people involved in artisanal production seem to value a healthy relation with resources, consumption and the ecosystem. Compared to other production systems, craft making seems to integrate a larger part of the value chain and feels closer to nature in that artisans often procure their own raw material and experiment continuously with it. This direct relation with their sources makes them very aware of the delicate balance between production and resource consumption.

Anna Maria San Jensen, a graduate from the Royal Danish Academy, states, "My work is about sustainability and I work with circularity, with waste materials. For example, I can make clay and glaze from what is seen as waste."

In Venice, **Valentina Stocco**, founder of "Regenerative Ceramics" envisions a startup that aims "to repurpose the discarded materials of these industries and give them a second life through the hands of talented artists." She notes that this approach would "reduce the need for new raw materials... reduce waste and preserve the natural resources." (see Figure 24)

Figure 24: Regenerative Ceramics: speculative sketch by Valentina Stocco

Anna Maria San Jensen describes their "eternal vessel" concept, inspired by Guatemalan communities, explaining that "when a community can sustain itself, enrich each other and grow, for me that's circularity and sustainability.". She further explains that the "eternal vessel" is about "how a vessel... which refills itself with what is inside, but also how it grows new dimensions with what is in there. And the impact grows, and the mental wellbeing grows and the sustainability of such a place, such a concept can grow." (see Figure 25).

Figure 25: *The Eternal Vessel: speculative sketch by Anna Maria Sand Jensen*

The Tellus Project by **Jocelin Veronese** is born from the idea of creating an object that "can retain, purify and release water based on needs," serving communities, individuals, and agriculture. The creator was "inspired by this object, the Moon, for its historical, symbolic and ultimately scientific level which affects the tides, therefore the water, so everything returns to being a bit in symbiosis with nature."

Figure 26: Tellus - speculative sketch by Jocelin Veronese

One reaction to the Brave New World exhibition was: "I think it's critically reflecting on the history in particular, like bringing up problematics that are connected to the current modes of production and consumption and in particular is rethinking what could be different compared to the current neoliberal point of views, economics and systems, production systems. Thus, thinking differently about alternative modes of consumption and production, it is very important and what could be done for the future. It is thinking about the future."

Another visitor calls for a redefinition of "progress" to include "multi species of progress with nature and redefine progress."

5.1.2 Moving Beyond Mass Production and Overconsumption

The tension between the values of craft and the methods of mass production was the main speculative topic of the Brave New World exhibition and something very present in the hearts and minds of all the artisans we interviewed.

Elena Rausse and Bruno Testa from Te.Ra. Design Studio highlight that the craftsman's vision "is in stark contrast to mass production full of optimization but devoid of soul." They explain that craftsmen incorporate "values of slowness and effective connection in the objects, in which one can recognize a constancy in thought, but not necessarily in the object, going to underline what is the value of imperfection as a sign of humanity." (see Figure 27).

Figure 27: Homo Factores - speculative sketch by Te.Ra. Design Studio

Jin Choi, a furniture designer and maker, imagines a world where "a design isn't created for a generic audience, but instead tailored to an individual's needs and desires. Where a design becomes more than just an object, it becomes a lifetime companion." (See Figure 28)

Figure 28: Craft Inquiry - speculative sketch by Jin Choi

Llora Fuente, a researcher at the University of Oviedo, identifies "the voracity of the consumption, in contemporary times" as one of the biggest challenges, noting that when consuming, people "don't think about the past, the creation, the process, the source of the materials. But also, we do not think about the future, the quality, the value of the piece versus the obsolete sense."

Figure 29: Craft Co-Lab - speculative sketch by Karl Hallberg

The Craft Collab Concept by **Karl Hallberg** envisions a world "where items would not be mass produced." Instead, furniture would be made of "better materials that are solid wood for example and would be very valuable. And this would create a need of repairing, maintaining and more of do it yourself kind of furniture that people would make for their homes." (see Figure 29).

Margot Bustamante, a researcher at Copenhagen Business School, suggests that "progress could also be that we start looking at all these other alternatives and incorporating them into and going away from mass production." They assert, "We are not over consuming but also not over producing. I think we, because we are consuming in a crazy way, we are also making ourselves produce knowledge work in a huge amount that is not sustainable even to ourselves and to our bodies. And then sickness, because of stress."

5.1.3 Fostering Community and Connection

As Richard Sennet (2008) notes in “the Craftsman”, an artisan only exists within a community. Craft people value relation, both within communities of fellow makers and in the larger local community they live in.

Anna Maria San Jensen observed in Guatemala "how communities, they were somehow interconnected and people from different aspects of a group or society, they were somehow benefiting each other." Their "eternal vessel" concept embodies how individuals "stand next to each other or if we refill each other with what we can teach a teacher, mentoring a student, something is refilled."

The Craft Collab Concept by **Karl Hallberg** proposes "stations or places around in the communities in housing areas where you can go and use tools together." The aim is to "achieve harder work together and you also create a community around achieving a goal, making your own furniture together with others. That creates a sense of belonging and a sense of ownership of the skills and of your situation."

The Venice Travel Experience concept by **Michela Bartolozzi** imagines travel as "connecting with a place rather than just passing through it absentmindedly." It proposes that travelers meet local craftspeople to "create an idea, an object, a project, something that did not exist before you met." The idea is that "If you haven't actually lived a place, then you have no proof that you've been there". (see Figure 30).

Figure 30: I'm a Traveler, therefore I respect - speculative sketch by Michela Bartolozzi

Nicola Pavan designed "The Hive," a building intended to be a "place of strong sharing, of strong community," housing laboratories where "professional craftsmen that will help shape new generations of creatives." They believe in this project because "craftsmanship in this way can help balance and make different disciplines coexist." (see Figure 31).

Figure 31: The Hive: speculative sketch by Nicola Pavan

The Library of Minds by **Nynne Rosenkrantz Christiansen** concept suggests a future where people could "direct feed ideas from your brain to a screen" and "join a group of people on screen and work out a problem, a project, find a solution visually, together." The author states this would be possible in "A world where people weren't afraid to share their ideas. A world where people would enjoy collaborating for everybody's best interest." An unusual take on technology that conveys in artistic terms the idea of a communitarian way of distilling knowledge, an AI for craft? (see Figure 32).

Figure 32: The Library of Minds: speculative sketch by Nynne Rosenkranz Christiansen

Anders Linders, a business man in Dals Långed, highlights how craft and cultural activities can counteract the decline of social meaning in former industrial areas, stating they "can both sort of make more sustainable products perhaps, but it also creates some kind of social cohesion which I think is that perhaps most valuable, the best value actually." They also stress that societal progress "has to be unified. It is not a progress of a certain strata of the society. So, it must be the complete society."

5.1.4 Valuing Craft and the Maker

Elena and Bruno from Terra Design Studio emphasize that a craftsman "still manages to incorporate a spirit within an object" by transmitting "his spirit, his experience, his daily life in his objects." They also value "imperfection as a sign of humanity."

The concept "As I Speak the Language of the Rhizosphere" by **Alberto Scodro** aims to "increase the visitor's awareness that when he is in front of an artistic object, he is actually looking at a whole series of hidden and invisible actions that made it possible."

Jokum Jensen, an artist blacksmith, acknowledges that their trade "invented and implemented the machines that powered the Industrial Revolution. But those machines also made my trade as an artist blacksmith in relation to architecture obsolete." He notes that since the 1980s, blacksmiths "have been trying to reinvent ourselves and become something that has a relevance for the society of today." (see Figure 33).

Figure 33: Re-Renaissance: speculative sketch by Jokum Lind Jensen

Nynne Rosenkrantz Christensen explains their approach: "I'm not trying to tell people anything. I am not trying to spell it out. But I want it to be part of the expression of what I make. And somehow I hope that people feel that expression and can take it in, and that is the way I can make a difference."

5.1.5 Knowledge, Skills, and Tools

There is an emphasis on the physical vs the digital: "You actually have to learn with your hands.", and one desire often expressed is for people to experience the benefits of manual, creative work.

The "Technique and Safety Committee" concept by Rob Curran (Swedish HEPHAESTUS craft ambassador) emphasizes the merit in "relevant and inspiring information and knowledge" from older literature, proposing a world where "this information in both methods of safety and technique when working within your craft, are published and available." This would establish a "foundation in craft... to connect hand and head." (see Figure 34).

Figure 34: Technique and Safety Committee: speculative sketch by Rob Curran

Elena and Bruno describe their symbolic "Craftsman's Backpack" as a container of "instrumental and cultural goods" that "is able to collect and contain memories, knowledge, but also materials that can be found along a path." They see the craftsman becoming "a sort of new hunter-gatherer in search of materials, techniques, tools that he can then use creatively within his work."

5.1.6 Redefining Progress and Time

Jokum Jensen questions, "I'm not sure that I think we are going towards progress in general with the way that society is going now.". They observe that students using AI for writing "will use words that I know that they don't know and they don't know what they mean.". They also anticipate a "counter reaction" within a few years from young people who will reject over-reliance on technology.

One visitor suggests "Progress would mean taking a step back but that can still be living a sustainable life financially wise and having time for what matters for the family and the friends and working in something that is having a good impact on them and the environment and the people that surround you.". This speaker also challenges the business school mantra that "Without innovation you die," noting that such innovation often leads to "a lot of waste".

Instead of "de-growth," a visitor proposes "craft growth or slow growth that allows everyone to reach the same prosperity," advocating for Western countries to "decrease the amount of goods produced" and rethink measures like GDP. They emphasize "taking time to live, to experience, to exist, to breathe. That might be a way more careful I think approach to progress." They also find positive value in living in a "slow" society like Bornholm, noting that "at any moment of the day you can find a different value for what you're doing." Another craftsperson suggests that "slowing time" or "stasis" can be a healthier way of thinking about progress, enabling one to "be in the present." They conclude, "The problem of progress is that we are always in progress. Every day, every minute is a progress. And we never can come back."

Figure 35: Formamia: speculative sketch by Pol Polloniato

Figure 36: As I speak the Language of the Rizosphere – speculative sketch by Alberto Scodro

Alberto Scodro asserts that "progress has to be unified. It is not a progress of a certain stratum of the society. So, it must be a complete society." They also note the disparity in technology use globally: "80% of people are not like us. So, we are 20% of the world that we are thinking and speaking and using technology. All the rest are living with nothing." (see Figure 36)

6.0 Future Outlook

For us, working with ABR methods (e.g., critical fabulation; speculative design methodologies; see Fried, 2025; Wang et al., 2017), as opposed to rather traditional methods, means recognizing that in our aesthetic choices and in the materials that draw us in, sometimes without a rational explanation, a form of thought is still present — only, very often, we had not yet listened to it or rationalized it. The practice is not just expression: it becomes a way of investigating the world and understanding that the entire process is a source of knowledge — non-linear, non-conclusive, but alive. Through video, images, sound, and music, we discovered relationships that a different analysis would not have revealed: a frame can become a question, an edit can generate a theory without stating it, and sound can tell a story without words.

This journey led us to ask ourselves: from where do I look? Why did I choose this image and not another? This voice or this sound? What moves me, or unsettles me, in the material I work with? This awareness does not serve to close meaning, but to open it. We learned that research does not lead to a definitive answer, but sharpens attention, awareness and generates new questions, which are often unexpected: what do I tell, and what remains outside? What have I understood, and what still escapes me?

In this regard, the dialogue with scholars and craft makers has been fundamental — a continuous play of reflections and echoes, of feedback that constantly generates new openings. The figure of the craftsperson gradually took on new layers of meaning, acquiring additional facets that offer a more complex and articulated reading. Art is not only a tool for research but also for connection, capable of creating unforeseen relationships between people, or between people and what surrounds them. Ideas and trajectories emerge from doing, from relationships, from intertwinings. It opened us to the awareness that ours is only one point of view, not *the* point of view, from which to tell a story.

Thanks to Critical Fabulation, we have tried to weave rigor and imagination in order to give space to what has not yet been explored — not to invent freely, but to repair a void, restore possibility, and reopen what seemed closed. For us, imagining also means creating: opening new spaces and new angles, fabricating possible futures that are not mere projections of the past, but scenarios capable of embracing the pluralities of the present and generating unprecedented forms of coexistence.

The final stage of the HEPHAESTUS project will be to tell, in documentary form, what we have understood — or believe we have understood — about the world of craft makers: its complexity, its dynamics, and its possible future trajectories. Furthermore, going forward, insights and prototypes developed within **Task 3.1** will directly contribute to the programming and testing phases of the Green Living Lab (WP5) and inform the development of educational methodologies in WP4. The documentary film developed under **Task 3.2** will also serve as a tool for communicating research processes and outcomes to wider audiences. Results will also feed dissemination and exploitation strategies in **WP6**, supporting policy dialogue, public engagement, and the long-term sustainability of the HEPHAESTUS network.

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